

THE STUDY OF COLLECTIBLE SAMPLES OF AGRICULTURAL CROPS IN THE CONDITIONS OF BOGARA IN THE SOUTH OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Annotation. The study of safflower varieties in the conditions of the Turkestan region. One of the promising oil-bearing plants for growing in changing natural conditions is safflower, the biology of which fully corresponds to the arid conditions of the steppe. This oil-bearing plant is ideal for local crop rotation, which contributes to the diversification of agricultural production. Safflower oil contains more linoleic acid and more vitamins than sunflower oil. And here, as is known, the source material is crucial, which requires constant updating, the introduction of new economically valuable genes and their complexes into it [2]. The world's plant genetic resources are considered worldwide as the main source of crop improvement for the coming decades. Since its foundation by N.I.Vavilov, VIR has been a methodological and methodological center in the field of fundamental and applied problems of crop production. Favorable conditions for the development of methodologies and research methods of the gene pool as a source and breeding material are created by the presence of a global gene pool for most of the leading crops.

Аннотация. Изучение сортов сафлора в условиях Туркестанского региона. Одним из перспективных масличных растений для выращивания в изменяющихся природных условиях является сафлор, биология которого полностью соответствует засушливым условиям степи. Это масличное растение идеально подходит для местного севооборота, что способствует диверсификации сельскохозяйственного производства. Сафлоровое масло содержит больше линолевой кислоты и больше витаминов, чем подсолнечное. И здесь, как известно, решающее значение имеет исходный материал, который требует постоянного обновления, введение в него новых хозяйственно ценных генов и их комплексов [2]. Мировые генетические ресурсы растений рассматриваются во всем мире как основной источник улучшения сельскохозяйственных культур на ближайшие десятилетия. С момента своего основания Н.И.Вавиловым ВИР являлся методологическим и методическим центром в области фундаментальных и прикладных проблем растениеводства. Благоприятные условия для развития методологий и методов исследований генофонда как исходного и селекционного материала создает наличие мирового генофонда по большинству ведущих культур.

Keywords: gene pool, wheat, barley, legumes, oilseeds, phenology, structural analysis, yield, stability.

Kalit so'zlar: aspir, harorat, urug'lar, quruq kontinental iqlim, vegetatsiya davri, potentsial hosil. genofond, bug'doy, arpa, dukkakli ekinlar, moyli o'simliklar, fenologiya, strukturaviy tahlil, hosildorlik, barqarorlik

Ключевые слова: сафлор, температура, семена, сухой континентальный климат, вегетационный период, потенциальная урожайность. генофонд, пшеница, ячмень, зернобобовые, масличные, фенология, структурный анализ, урожайность, устойчивость

Xulosa. Turkiston mintaqasida aspir navlarini o'rganish. O'zgaruvchan tabiiy sharoitda etishtirish uchun istiqbolli moyli o'simliklardan biri aspir bo'lib, uning biologiyasi dashtning quruq sharoitlariga to'liq mos keladi. Bu moyli o'simlik mahalliy almashlab ekish uchun juda mos keladi, bu esa qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishini diversifikatsiya qilishga yordam beradi. Aspir yog'i kungaboqar yog'iga qaraganda ko'proq linoleik kislota va ko'proq vitaminlarga ega. Va bu erda, siz bilganingizdek, doimiy yangilanishni, unga yangi iqtisodiy jihatdan qimmatli genlar va ularning komplekslarini kiritishni talab qiladigan boshlang'ich material juda muhimdir [2]. Dunyo bo'ylab o'simliklarning genetik resurslari butun dunyo bo'ylab kelgusi o'n yilliklar davomida ekinlarni yaxshilashning asosiy manbai sifatida qaraladi. N. I. Vavilov VIR tashkil topganidan beri o'simlikchilikning fundamental va amaliy muammolari sohasidagi uslubiy va uslubiy markaz bo'lib kelgan. Genofondni boshlang'ich va selektiv material sifatida o'rganish metodologiyasi va usullarini rivojlantirish uchun qulay shart-sharoitlar etakchi ekinlarning ko'pchiligida jahon genofondining mavjudligi bilan yaratiladi.

Introduction. The strategy of conservation and active use of plant genetic resources in breeding is based on accurate methods of identification and registration of the gene pool. Consideration of all aspects of the dynamics of cultural and wild flora is associated with changes in the biosphere, and the anticipation of measures to prevent the loss of particularly valuable species and forms. In recent years, it has become increasingly clear that there is a need to strengthen measures to preserve ancient varieties and natural populations in their natural state (in situ), as a potential source of genetic improvement and improvement of the modern varietal gene pool. A method of long-term storage of seeds of collection samples of agricultural crops in various packages will be developed. The prevailing models of agricultural development have led to environmental pollution, overexploitation of land and water resources, which eventually caused soil erosion and salinization, degradation of pastures, and reduction of local agrobiodiversity [1]. Reducing varietal diversity not only reduces the resistance of agroecosystems to weather fluctuations, but also significantly increases their genetic vulnerability, which is based on an increase in the genetic uniformity of varieties and hybrids, which will lead to the disappearance of traditional local varieties and indigenous forms and ultimately endanger food security in the world. And here, as is known, the source material is crucial, which requires constant updating, the introduction of new economically valuable genes and their complexes into it [2]. The world's plant genetic resources are considered worldwide as the main source of crop improvement for the coming decades. Since its foundation by N.I.Vavilov, VIR has been a methodological and methodological center in the field of fundamental and applied problems of crop production. Favorable conditions for the development of methodologies and research methods of the gene pool as a source and breeding material are created by the presence of a global gene pool for most of the leading crops. In the history of VIR, this has been realized in the development of genetics, plant immunity, physiology, biochemistry, and technological assessment in relation to the problems of source and breeding material.

Purpose: replenishment of the gene pool of agricultural crops with 38 samples of cereals, 10 samples of legumes, 12 samples of oilseeds.

Research method: Formation and sowing of collection nurseries - according to the regulation "On collections of plant resources of the VIR" - Leningrad: VIR, 1964. Preparation and storage of the collection according to the instructions "Laying seeds of collection samples for long-term storage in a closed container" - Leningrad: VIR, 1971. Determination of the viability of stored collections according to the methodological guidelines "Determination of the growth force of grain seeds by morphophysiological assessment of seedlings" - Leningrad: VIR, 1975. Documentation is carried out in accordance with the "Guidelines for the formation of a database on plant genetic resources" - Aleppo: ICARDA, 2005.

Soil and climatic characteristics of the study area Site description – coordinates No.41.468580, E069,45039 0, soil – light gray, humus content 1.1%. The territory of the South Kazakhstan region, amounting to 121.51 thousand square kilometers, is located in the foothill desert-steppe zone of the Tien Shan, which is significantly removed from the sources of atmospheric moisture - the oceans, and therefore the climate is characterized by pronounced continentally [3]. The amount of average annual precipitation is 200-700 mm, which is why the rainfed lands of the region are conditionally divided into three zones: - unsecured rainfed (300-450 m . above sea level) with precipitation of 250 mm; - semi-secured rainfed (height 450-600 m) with precipitation of 400-600 mm; - secured rainfed (height 600-1500 m) with precipitation of more than 600 mm. Thus, the spring period for the main vegetation periods of plant growth in April and May, and climatic weather conditions in general for chickpeas were favorable because in the month of March 2022, the amount of precipitation was 105.5 mm higher than long-term precipitation. Thus, the growth and development of plants accelerated. As a result of a sharp increase in temperature, many early- and medium-ripened cultivars bloomed together during the growing season and the beans were well formed. Summing up the results of the agricultural year, it should be noted that due to the lack of precipitation in the form of a downpour during the period of intensive plant growth, the year was unfavorable for the growth and development of plants.

Table 1

Months	Precipitation. 2022-2023	Precipitation for many years (mm)	Precipitation difference	Temperature of 2021- 2022	Temperature of many year	Temperature difference
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
September	0,0	3,0	-3,0	23,3	20,8	+2,5
October	34,4	27	+7,4	11,7	13,8	-2,1
November	26,7	44	-17,3	6,2	6,8	-0,6
Total	61,1	74,0	-12,9	12,3	13,8	-1,5
December	41,9	57	-15,1	6,4	2,4	+1,4
January	50,0	48	+2,0	4,0	1,7	+1
February	55,5	55	+0,5	5,2	2,5	+6,4
Total	147,4	160,0	-12,6	5,2	+2,2	+3,0
March	179,5	74	+105,5	7,8	7,0	+0,8
April	14,8	61	-46,2	20,1	14,4	+5,7
May	69,9	37	+32,9	20,8	19,2	+1,6
total	264,2	172,0	+92,2	16,2	13,5	+2,7
June	2,7	10,0	-10,0	27,2	25,1	+2,1

July	-	3,0	-3,0	29,2	28,2	+1,0
August	-	2,0	-2,0	26,1	26,4	-0,3
total	2,7	15,0	-11,3	27,5	26,5	+1,0
Total	475,4	421,0	+54,4			

Research results 10 wheat varieties from the VIR collections were used for sowing, including varieties from Turkey (SONMEZ), varieties from Kyrgyzstan (Zhamin, Dordoy 16), from Tajikistan: varieties (DURAKHSHON, GANJ), varieties from Russia (Kuma, Kroshka), varieties from Uzbekistan (Sanzar 6, Tanya), from the Serbian variety (Rapsodiya), the standard variety is the local variety Memory-47.

Table 2 - Growing season of wheat collection samples.

№:	Name of varieties	Origin	Data of heading	Data of flowering	Data of maturity
1	Память 47 ст.	KAZ	16.04.2022	09.05.2022	29.06.2022
2	Zhamin	KGZ	25.04.2022	25.05.2022	27.06.2022
3	Dordoy 16	KGZ	24.04.2022	26.05.2022	29.06.2022
4	DURAKHSHON	TAJ	17.04.2022	10.05.2022	30.06.2022
5	GANJ	TAJ	19.04.2022	09.05.2022	30.06.2022
6	Kuma	RF	15.04.2022	09.05.2022	30.06.2022
7	Kroshka	RF	22.04.2022	10.05.2022	29.06.2022
8	Sanzar 6	UZ	14.04.2022	07.05.2022	30.06.2022
9	Tanya	UZ	14.04.2022	08.05.2022	29.06.2022
10	Rapsodiya	SRB	22.04.2022	23.05.2022	28.06.2022
11	SONMEZ	TUR	14.05.2022	09.05.2022	29.06.2022

In bogara conditions, due to the sudden onset of heat during the ripening period, it is difficult to determine the ripening phase, since all samples turn yellow at the same time for 2-3 days. Therefore, we focus on precocity at the time of earing, according to this feature, the varieties Kuma, Sansar 6 and Tanya have identified a standard variety for 1-2 days.

Table 3- Growing season of collection samples of barley

№:	Name of varieties	Origin	Data of heading	Data of flowering	Data of maturity
1	Bereke -54 (local check)	KAZ	25.04.22	05.05.22	20.06.22
2	Maxsim	TUR	27.04.22	08.05.22	22.06.22
3	Lokedor	TUR	28.04.22	10.05.22	26.06.22
4	Vodopad -100	KAZ	20.04.22	04.05.22	20.06.22
5	Vodopad-17	KAZ	20.04.22	04.05.22	20.06.22
6	Tlek	KAZ	25.04.22	05.05.22	24.06.22
7	Kazgurt	KAZ	25.04.22	05.05.22	24.06.22
8	Bogara	KAZ	22.04.22	04.05.22	20.06.22
9	Jebe	KAZ	21.04.22	04.05.22	20.06.22
10	Ujnkazakhstanskaya 43	KAZ	23.04.22	08.05.22	26.06.22
11	En-270	SUR	24.04.22	08.05.22	26.06.22

Promising varieties Vodopad-100, Vodopad 1-17, Bogara, Zhebe of Krasnovodopadsky breeding showed early maturity for barley.

Grain crops were sown on October 20, 2021 in Bogar, the first wheat seedlings were received on December 15, barley from December 25, tillering began on February 10, 2022. The tubulation phase began in barley on March 23 and wheat on April 2. According to the phase of the onset of earing, Uzbek wheat varieties (Sanzar 6, Tanya) and Turkish varieties (SONMEZ) were distinguished on 04/14/2022. among the barley, promising varieties Waterfall-100 and Waterfall-17 were planted 5 days earlier than the standard. The ripening of barley began on June 20, wheat at the end of June.

Table 4- The growing season of collection samples of safflower.

№ п/п	Сортообразцы	Origin	Data of 6 leaf phase	Data of branches	Data of flowering
1	Nurlan (local chek).	KAZ	15.04.22	21.05.22.	20.06.22
2	LC-33	SUR	15.04.22	21.05.22.	20.06.22
3	K-1183-10-13	MEX	16.04.22	20.05.22.	20.06.22
4	K-92-53-28	MEX	16.04.22	20.05.22.	21.06.22
5	K-286	MEX	14.04.22	19.05.22.	18.06.22
6	U-19	UZ	16.04.22	22.05.22.	21.06.22
7	LC-94	SUR	17.04.22	25.05.22.	22.06.22
8	K-8026	MEX	17.04.22	22.05.22.	22.06.22
9	K-53	MEX	18.04.22	23.05.22.	22.06.22
10	K-80-12-40	MEX	16.04.22	23.05.22.	21.06.22
11	LC-78/3	SUR	12.04.22	20.05.22.	19.06.22

For safflower, 8 samples from the collections of ICARDA-Turkey were used for sowing, including from Syria numbers (LC-33, LC-94, LC-78/3), from Uzbekistan numbers (U-19), from Mexico varieties (K-1183-10-13 , K-92-53-28, K-286, K-8026, K-53, K-80-12-40) the standard variety is the local safflower variety Nurlan. According to the offensive phase, safflower samples K-286 from Mexico LC-78/3 from Syria flowering safflower samples K-286 from Mexico LC-78/3 from Syria. The samples were cleaned in July, all samples were manually mowed with a sickle and labelled on the field, further work was carried out in laboratories. 5 plants with roots were excavated from all the samples for structural analysis. A structural analysis was carried out, measuring the height of the stem, the length of the ear-bearing internode, the length of the ear. The number of productive stems, the number of grains in the ear, the grain weight of the 1st plant, the grain weight per 1 square meter and other characteristics of the samples were determined.

Table 5 Structural analysis of wheat samples.

№ п/п	Name of varieties	Origin	1000 kernel weight (gr)	Grain weight per plant (gr)	Grain weight per 1m ² (gr)
1	Pamyat 47 (local check).	KAZ	34,4	4,97	251,2
2	Zhamin	KGZ	23,6	4,13	111,5
3	Dordoy 16	KGZ	31,5	6,09	201,0
4	DURAKHSHON	TAJ	36,7	3,40	224,0
5	GANJ	TAJ	42,1	4,12	101,1

6	Kuma	RF	32,1	5,17	134,0
7	Kroshka	RF	41,6	7,20	287,2
8	Sanzar 6	UZ	44,4	7,83	281,5
9	Tanya	UZ	37,1	5,31	114,3
10	Rapsodiya	SRB	35,1	6,41	203,8
11	SONMEZ	TUR	33,7	4,13	154,0
SSD _{0,95}					21,4

The determination of the mass of 1000 grains was carried out in an Adventurer scale, a sign of grain mass is an indicator of drought resistance. According to this feature, mainly varieties from Uzbekistan Sanjar-4 – 44.6 g., from Tajikistan grade GANJ-42.1 g. After recalculation, the weight of grains from 1 square meter Kroshka and Sanzar- 6 showed grain yields above 28 c /ha.

Conclusions. Replenishment of the gene pool of agricultural crops with 20 samples of cereals, 10 samples of legumes, 10 samples of oilseeds. Assessment of collections on economically valuable grounds, preservation of collections, creation of an information database, organization of storage. 10 wheat varieties from the VIR collections were used for sowing, including from Turkey varieties (SONMEZ), from Kyrgyzstan varieties (Zhamin, Dordoy 16), from Tajikistan: varieties (DURAKHSHON, GANJ), from Russia varieties (Kuma, Kroshka), from Uzbekistan varieties (Sanzar 6, Tanya), from the Serbian variety (Rapsodiya), the standard variety is the local variety Memory-47. According to the phase of the onset of earing, Uzbek wheat varieties (Sanzar 6, Tanya) and Turkish varieties (SONMEZ) were distinguished on 04/14/2022. among the barley, promising varieties Waterfall-100 and Waterfall-17 were planted 5 days earlier than the standard. The ripening of barley began on June 20, wheat at the end of June. According to the flowering phase, safflower samples K-286 from Mexico LC-78/3 from Syria were isolated, F-97-122C and LC-263 from Syria were isolated from chickpeas. According to the high mass of 1000 barley grains, promising varieties of Krasnovodopadsky breeding varieties Waterfall-100-56.7g, and Bogara-61.4g were identified. After recalculation, the grain weight from 1 square meter of the Kroshka and Sanzar 6 varieties showed grain yields above 28 c/ha. Among the barley varieties Waterfall-100, Kazygurt, Bogara showed grain yields above 29 c/ha. When determining the mass of 1000 safflower grains, K samples were isolated-1183-10-13- 40,1 G., and K-8026-42.1 grams from Mexico. The low index in samples K-286 is 32.1g. and LC-94 is 32.1g. Among the varieties and numbers of chickpeas, LC-263 is 430.1g, Yubileyny is 414 - 400.2g. and Zhanalyk is 450.1g.

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